

State Management of Salaries in Enterprises in Vietnam

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Abstract : Based on the research of the legal framework on salary in enterprises in Vietnam, the information collected and evaluated from the state management agencies on salaries and survey data of 40 enterprises; the study has focused on analyzing the state management of salary in enterprises in Vietnam in the period of 2013-2019 with the following main contents: formulating and implementing salary policies in enterprises; inspecting and examining the implementation of policies; the state's supporting role for enterprises in this field. The study showed the successes and limitations of the state management of salaries in enterprises in Vietnam, and proposed recommendations and solutions to improve the state management of salaries in enterprises in Vietnam in the coming time.

Keywords: State management, salaries, Vietnam

I. INTRODUCTION

State management of salary in enterprises in Vietnam has been much renovated. Especially since 2013, The birth of the National Salary Council marked a great improvement in the mechanism of minimum salary determination in Vietnam. Beside that, Decree 49/ND-CP dated May 14, 2013 of the Government detailing a number of articles of the Labor Code, renewing the regulations on payroll scale and labor norms in enterprises. Also since 2013, salary management for state-owned enterprises has changed significantly.

These innovations have brought many important achievements in the state management of salaries in enterprises such as creating opportunities for enterprises to autonomously negotiate collectively, designing salary policies in accordance with the conditions of each enterprise, contributing to promoting competition as well as improving the efficiency of production and business of enterprises. However, the current minimum salary policy for enterprises still faces some shortcomings. The principles of salary scale construction and labor norms are still rigid and not really consistent with reality. Some regulations for state-owned enterprises still make it difficult to build the salary system of this enterprise, etc. Dialogue and collective bargaining on periodic salary in enterprises are still limited.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1. Literature review

Salary state management is studied by many domestic and foreign experts. Mirandan Kwong (2017), labor economics expert of ILO Office in Vietnam, pointed out the main inequality at global, regional and national levels as well as showed the correlation between minimum salary and inequality of salaries (including emphasis on real salaries, including institutional, policy, economic and social factors). The author also raises questions about the impact of minimum salaries on workers and businesses, institutions establishing minimum salaries and collective bargaining on salaries, and the relevance of salary policy and other socio-economic policies [1]. Matle Luebker (2014), Regional Senior Expert on Wages of the ILO Asia-Pacific Regional Office, asserts that institutions that determine good salaries need: (1) Salaries floor to protect people labor from being overpaid, (2) Strong collective bargaining brought salary increases along with increased productivity in industries and businesses [2]. John Ritchotte (2014), an industrial relations expert who gave Vietnam advice as follows: (1) Negotiating salary should be based on the performance and labor productivity of enterprises and workers; (2) The negotiation is very difficult and time-consuming, so it is necessary to proceed immediately (3) Emphasize the role of the Government to provide a legal framework that is not too rigid in detail but strong enough to allow negotiations to take place [3]. Richad Anker (2014) analyzes and assesses methods for determining the minimum living needs of workers in Vietnam and makes recommendations to improve estimates of minimum living needs [4].

In domestic, Thi Minh Tong (2010) has clarified the theoretical and practical basis for renewing the content of State management of salary in various types of enterprises in the period of 2011-2020, identifying the objectives,

principles, contents and propose solutions to renovate the contents of State management of salaries in all types of Vietnamese enterprises by 2020 [5].

Quang Vinh Dao (2007) has analyzed the factors affecting the salary - income distribution relationship of various types of enterprises, assessing the salary - income distribution mechanism in three types of enterprises in the 2001-2005 period and has recommended solutions to improve the distribution of salaries and incomes in the types of enterprises in the 2006-2010 period to ensure economic development and social justice [6]. Thi Nhan Huynh et al (2007) mentioned social equity in salary and income distribution and given the system of criteria for social justice in salary and income distribution. The author also clarified the status of ensuring equality in salary and income distribution and proposing viewpoints and solutions to ensure equality in the distribution of salaries and incomes among types of enterprises [7].

In summary, the above studies have shown a general picture of salary distribution as well as the content of state management of wages in enterprises. These research projects have both theoretical and practical significance.

2.2. Theoretical background

State management is the management in which the managing entity is the state. The state affects the management object or the managing object to achieve the state's goal. State management appears with the appearance of the state. State management changes depending on the political regime, the level of socio-economic development of each country through historical periods.

State management of enterprises is an intentional, organized and equitable impact of the state. Through a system of policies, management tools, the state manages the enterprise system in order to make the most effective use of resources for economic development, achieving the socio-economic development goals of the country.

According to Thi Minh Tong (2010), State management of salary in enterprises is a form of state management, the management subject is the state, central agencies, localities and the management object is every enterprise. The State uses the law to regulate the operational behavior of enterprises in the field of salaries, in order to satisfy the legitimate needs of enterprises and employees, maintain stability and social development. State management of salaries in enterprises includes: the promulgation of legal provisions specifying the basic obligations of business owners to employees in the field of salaries; professional guidance on building labor norms, enterprise salary system. At the same time, it is also responsible for checking, inspecting and urging the strict implementation of the salary regulations, as well as carrying out activities to promote the improvement and development of the salary system in the enterprise [5].

The content of state management on salaries in enterprises may have different approaches. Within this topic, state management of salary in enterprises is accessible according to three main contents, namely: policy formulation and implementation; inspecting and examining the implementation of policies; support and consult businesses to improve the capacity of salary policy formulation and enhance collective bargaining capacity on salary.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

The article uses a combination of qualitative research methods and quantitative research methods with many different data sources.

- Secondary information source: synthesized from topics, reports at seminars, statistics from the General Statistics Office, related research works and reports of enterprises, decrees, circulars, official dispatches and State management documents on salaries in enterprises for the period of 2013 - 2018.

- Primary information source:

+ Investigating in 50 enterprises (including 5 state-owned enterprises with 100% capital, 5 state-owned enterprises with more than 50% capital, 15 FDI enterprises and 15 joint-stock companies), each enterprise 6 votes (1 vote for trade union officials, 2 officials for human resources management, salary and labor and 1 vote for business leaders).

+ Survey results generated 160 votes (40 leadership votes, 40 union officials votes, 80 Labor - Salary officials votes), the results obtained 153 valid votes (40 leadership votes, 40 votes union officials, 73 workers' salary votes).

+ Interview with State management officials on salaries of ministries and branches; interviews with local managers, trade union officials at all levels, officials at enterprises' organizations

+ Workshop to get opinions of experts and stakeholders.

IV. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Actual state of salary management in Vietnamese enterprises

4.1.1. The reality of the legal framework

Regarding the minimum salary

According to the provisions of the Labor Code, the regional minimum salary applies to employees working in enterprises, unions of cooperatives, cooperatives, cooperative groups, farms, households and individuals, agencies and

organizations employing laborers under contracts. From 2013 to present, the regional minimum salary is adjusted annually (Table 1).

Table 1. Regional minimum salaries, period 2013 - 2019

Unit: VND / month

Decree	Date of issuance	Date of application	Region 1	Region 2	Region 3	Region 4
103/2012/NĐ-CP	04/12/2012	01/01/2013	2.350.000	2.100.000	1.800.000	1.650.000
182/2013/NĐ-CP	14/11/2013	31/12/2013	2.700.000	2.400.000	2.100.000	1.900.000
103/2014/NĐ-CP	11/11/2014	01/01/2015	3.100.000	2.750.000	2.400.000	2.150.000
122/2015/NĐ-CP	14/11/2015	01/01/2016	3.500.000	3.100.000	2.700.000	2.400.000
153/2016/NĐ-CP	14/11/2016	01/01/2017	3.750.000	3.320.000	2.900.000	2.580.000
141/2017/NĐ-CP	07/12/2017	25/01/2018	3.980.000	3.530.000	3.090.000	2.760.000
157/2018/NĐ-CP	16/11/2018	01/01/2019	4.180.000	3.710.000	3.250.000	2.920.000

Source: collected by authors

The application of regional minimum salaries shall comply with the principle: Enterprises located in any region shall apply the minimum regional salary; The regional minimum salary rates are set by the Government as the lowest salaries to be paid to workers performing the simplest jobs under normal working conditions in enterprises; For employees who have vocational training (including those taught by enterprises themselves), the enterprises must be at least 7% higher than the regional minimum salary. The state encourages enterprises to implement minimum salaries higher than the regional minimum salary set by the state, etc [8].

Results of a survey of 40 enterprises, on ensuring the minimum living standard of the minimum salary, had 107/153 opinions (accounting for 69.9%) answered "with guarantee" and 46/153 comments (accounting for 30.1%) answered "no guarantee". With the responses as "guaranteed", assessing the minimum living standard for employees of the regional minimum salary, there are 10/107 opinions (accounting for 9%) assessing the level of security. very low rating, 10/277 reviews (accounting for 25%) rated at a low level, there are 52/107 comments (accounting for 49%) rated at an average, 18/107 comments (accounted for 17%) rated at high and no reviews are very high.

However, it is a fact that currently there are many workers working in family business households, freelance workers, working in small economic zones, they do not have labor contracts and are not guaranteed. About the minimum salary as prescribed by the state.

When asked whether the current minimum salary regulation harmonizes the interests of employees and employers, 64/153 (accounting for 42%) answered "yes". In which, there are 12 opinions (accounting for 8%) of business leaders, 15 ideas (accounting for 10%) of trade union officials and 37 opinions (accounting for 24%) of workers - salaries. The remaining 89/153 opinions (accounting for 58%) answered "no".

Regarding the time to adjust the minimum salary, 97/153 opinions (63%) considered it appropriate and 56/153 comments (47%) considered inappropriate (too short).

Regarding salary scale, payroll

The Government issued Decree No. 49/2013 / ND-CP on May 14, 2013. Accordingly, all enterprises are entitled to build their own payroll scales on the basis of compliance with the principles in this Decree. Some basic principles of the Decree: (1) Enterprises build and decide the salary scale and payroll; (2) The difference between the two adjacent salary steps must be at least 5%; (3) The lowest salary for a simple job or title in ordinary working conditions shall not be lower than the regional minimum salary as set by the Government; (4) The lowest salary for a job or job title requiring trained, apprenticeship workers (including those taught by enterprises) must be at least 7% higher than the regional minimum salary due to Government regulations; (5) The salary of the job or title with heavy, hazardous and dangerous working conditions must be at least 5% higher; extremely heavy, hazardous and dangerous jobs must be at least 7% higher than the salaries of jobs or titles of similar complexity, working in normal working conditions; (6) When establishing and applying the salary scale, the payroll must ensure equality, and must set standards for salary classification and conditions for raising salary grades; (7) The salary scale and payroll must be periodically reviewed for amendments and supplements [8]. When building, amending or supplementing an enterprise, it must consult the representative organization of the labor collective at the enterprise and make it public at the workplace before implementation. In addition, Decree 49/2013 / ND-CP also stipulates the principle of setting labor norms in enterprises.

Decree 49/2013 / ND-CP was issued to fundamentally change the salary system, ladders and payrolls of enterprises. Highlights of the Decree are that businesses are allowed to build their own payroll scales according to their positions and jobs. However, the determination of the salary gap between two adjacent levels or the salary gap between jobs with different working conditions in the Decree is still rigid, causing difficulties for enterprises.

Regarding salary and income management

The state has institutionalized a view on salary payment and salary distribution in a market economy, which is mainly distributed according to labor results and economic efficiency. The law stipulates that salaries are paid to employees based on productivity and quality of work; enterprises are allowed to decide on their own the distribution and payment of salaries in accordance with the quantity and quality of labor contributed by employees.

For state-owned enterprises holding dominant shares, the content of state management of salaries is specified in Decree No. 51/2016 / ND-CP, Decree No. 52/2016 / ND-CP, Decree No. 53/2016 / ND-CP of the Government. All 3 Decrees have a transparent spirit of associating labor productivity with salaries and bonuses. However, according to the Ministry of Labor, War Invalids and Social Affairs' salary policy reform policy for production and business areas, due to the fact that it has not calculated and compared the actual efficiency among state-owned enterprises; therefore, some businesses earn 2-3 times higher than the average, but not entirely due to high productivity and efficiency [9].

4.1.2. The situation of implementation of salary policies in enterprises and the role of state inspection and examination

The situation of minimum salary implementation

According to the survey results, 100% of enterprises apply the lowest salary in accordance with the state's regulations on regional minimum salary. However, businesses also believe that the increase of regional minimum salary has affected the company's salary policy, affecting the salary relationship between labor types and job positions. Thereby, it makes it difficult for businesses to adjust salaries, as well as create pressure on salary costs and social insurance and health insurance premiums (for enterprises with low salary policies).

Regarding the implementation of the salary scale and payroll

Enterprises have been interested in building ladders and payrolls and have sent salary scales and payrolls to local labor management agencies. For businesses operating effectively, doing business, the management of labor - salaries is done quite methodically. The enterprise has built a ladder and payroll in line with its production and business practices and ensures competition in the market. However, there are still businesses that do not send pay scales and payrolls to local management agencies. Quite a lot of businesses built ladders and payrolls at the lowest level, close to the floor prescribed by the Law.

According to the survey results, 50% of enterprises have built payroll scales according to their positions; 25% of businesses implement payroll scale according to 3P; 12.5% of businesses review and revise the payroll scale of Decree 205/2004 / ND-CP to ensure compliance with a number of provisions of Decree 49 / ND-CP; and 12.5% of enterprises do not set payroll scales but pay as agreed upon. The number of enterprises with the gap between 2 adjacent salaries in the salary scale is at least 5%, accounting for 46.15%; 53.85% of enterprises have the difference between 2 adjacent steps in the salary scale of 6-8%. 100% of enterprises have built salary scales taking into account working conditions.

Regarding regulations on the principle of salary scale construction, most of the assessments are not appropriate (accounting for 66.67%), only 33.33% of the comments are appropriate. The nonconformities expressed in enterprises were restricted from the right to take the initiative to build the payrolls (45%), affecting the structure of the scales and payrolls (accounting for 36%), creating pressure on costs for enterprises (accounting for 27%), and 9% said that they do not encourage salary payment.

The main cause of difficulties for businesses when building ladders and payrolls by enterprises reflects that: there is a shortage of staff to build payrolls (accounting for 73.98%), inadequate officials to build (accounting for 84.93%), without the state's guiding documents (54.79%) (Table 2).

Table 2. Causes of difficulties for enterprises in building payroll scale

Difficulties in building payroll scales of businesses	Number of votes	Rate
Insufficient capacity to be able to build themselves	62	84,93
Lack of staff to do this	54	73,98
There are no governmental guidelines	40	54,79
Not supported by superiors	44	60,27
There is no time to do this	28	38,36

Source: collected by authors

Also according to the survey results, the number of enterprises thought that it is not necessary to send ladders and payrolls to state management agencies (accounting for 67%); The number of respondents who did not receive support from agencies at all levels (accounted for 57%), and did not receive feedback from the authorities (accounting for 42%).

Plans for payment of salaries and incomes of employees

There are 29/40 enterprises (accounting for 72.5%) pay salary based on the performance of work; There are 21/40 enterprises (accounting for 52.5%) paying salary based on their capacity and 32/40 enterprises (accounting for 80%) are paying salary based on the position / job title. Most enterprises combine many factors to develop a payment plan (Results of a survey of 40 enterprises).

Regarding the pay period, 37/40 enterprises (accounting for 92.5%) paid in time and in accordance with regulations; 2/40 enterprises said that enterprises that sometimes pay late salaries have interest compensation (accounting for 5%), and 1/40 enterprises pay late salaries, not compensating with interest (accounting for 2.5%).

Collective bargaining on salaries

Collective bargaining on salaries plays an important role in building a harmonious and stable relationship in enterprises. Effective collective bargaining will reduce labor disputes and strikes. Currently, in addition to enterprises that perform well in collective bargaining, there are businesses that have been dealing with labor disputes and strikes for many reasons. In particular, the ability to bargain collectively on salary is one of the common causes.

According to the statistics of the Ministry of Labor, War Invalids and Social Affairs, by the end of 2016, collective stoppages and strikes occurred the most in foreign-invested enterprises with more than 2,530 (accounting for more than 73%). private enterprises occurred 885 (accounting for 25%), state-owned enterprises were 25.

In the first 10 days of 2018, 05 strikes occurred. According to Mr. Thanh Hai Tran (inspector of the Ministry of Labor, War Invalids and Social Affairs) *"The causes of collective suspension are mainly related to salaries and Tet bonuses such as enterprises that owe salary, do not pay bonuses. Tet holiday or Tet bonus payment is less than committed, unfair Tet bonuses for different types of laborers,..."*

The number and size of collective stoppages and strikes in businesses are quite large, especially FDI and private enterprises. The cause of the strikes is mainly on salaries. Laborers are discontent about salaries, bonuses, remuneration, time to pay ... Survey data also shows that FDI enterprises, the efficiency of collective bargaining on salaries is the lowest ; followed by private joint stock companies and then state-owned enterprises with 50% equity and 100% equity.

State inspection and examination on implementation of salary policy in enterprises

Inspecting and examining the implementation of salary policies at enterprises assigned by the State to the Labor, War Invalids and Social Affairs Inspectorate. In 04 years from 2013 to 2016, the Ministry Inspectorate conducted a regional inspection of compliance with the provisions of labor law, social insurance and gender equality at 466 enterprises. Through inspection, the Chief Inspector of the Ministry has issued 5,005 petitions to request enterprises to implement; issued 46 sanctioning decisions with a total amount of VND 792 million [10].

Inspection of compliance with the provisions of the labor law at 12 corporations / corporations / companies and 161 member units. Through inspection, the Chief Inspector of the Ministry issued 2,666 petitions, 07 sanctioning decisions with a total amount of 109 million.

MOLISA inspectors in provinces and cities under central authority conducted 338 administrative inspections, through inspections, more than 1,850 petitions were proposed to be requested for implementation.

The total number of specialized inspections carried out in 04 years was 30,256, including labor: 11,630. Some major violations such as: not fully comply with the periodic reporting regime to the state labor management authority; The content of the labor contract does not specify the rights and obligations of the employee; the process of negotiating and signing collective labor agreements is not in accordance with the regulations; no payroll regulations and bonuses have been set up for management officials; Overtime pay for night work, weekends, holidays and holidays is not sufficient [10].

In general, the inspection and examination work has been strengthened and strengthened. A state specialized labor inspection system has been established with more than 430 labor inspectors from central to local levels. Some localities have strengthened the labor inspectors (Ho Chi Minh City from 18 to 30, Dong Nai from 09 to 17, Binh Duong from 6 to 10).

Inspection and examination have contributed to raising the awareness of labor law observance by enterprises and workers. Activity bar, inspection has also gradually renovated the form. However, state inspection and inspection activities still reveal limitations such as: The number of labor inspectors is low (only about 40% of the required number compared to the number of enterprises); The quality of officials and inspectors has not met the requirements and assigned tasks; Regulations on the order of conducting an inspection reveal many limitations and shortcomings; Labor inspectors are mainly concentrated at central and provincial levels. The capacity of labor inspection officials remains uneven between central and local levels, between localities.

4.1.3. Situation of the role of state support and consultancy for businesses and stakeholders in capacity building and implementation of salary policies in enterprises

In addition to issuing relevant legal documents, conducting supervision and inspection of law enforcement of enterprises. The role of governmental support and advice to enterprises in developing salary policies and the capacity for collective bargaining on salaries is very important.

The study shows that the government has not conducted a survey on training needs, advice, support to improve the professional capacity of enterprises. The State has organized training courses, guidelines for developing salary policies and collective bargaining on salaries (according to the survey results, 92/153 respondents said the state has conducted training (accounting for 60.13%). However, the main content of the training courses is to guide newly decrees, circulars and legal documents. The coverage is not high, the reception of information on training courses not yet covered on a large scale. As a result, some leaders and officials are unaware of this information.

Assessing the content, training programs, state guidelines to meet the practical needs of businesses, most of the opinions said that the main training content to solve for businesses to understand and do the law, not meeting the requirements of improving in-depth competence, skill in building salary system, collective bargaining in enterprises (accounting for 90%).

4.1.4. General assessment of state management of salary in enterprises in Vietnam

Researching the situation of state management of salary in enterprises in Vietnam and drawing some following assessments:

Achievements:

Considered salary in the enterprise as labor cost. The minimum salary regulation is the lowest salary to serve as a basis for enterprises and employees to agree on a salary.

State management of salaries in enterprises has contributed to better protecting the rights of workers in the context of limited collective bargaining in enterprises. Creating favorable conditions and mechanisms to promote the completion of the enterprise's salary policy, contributing to building harmonious and stable labor relations in the enterprise.

Institutions have a view on salary and income distribution. In particular, clarifying the need to distribute salaries, income according to the position, labor productivity, working efficiency of employees, business performance of the business. Gradually give autonomy to businesses in the construction of payroll scales, salary and income distribution.

The State has conducted salary inspections and checks in enterprises. The salary inspection and examination of enterprises has contributed to enhancing the compliance with the salary law of enterprises.

Limitations

The legalizing on minimum salary in the enterprise sector still has many unreasonable, unclear details, and does not represent the proper role and function of the minimum salary. Criteria for determining minimum salary are too emphasizing minimum living needs. The coverage of minimum salaries is low. Adjusting the minimum salary has no clear roadmap, making it difficult for some businesses. The minimum hourly salary has not been set to meet the current job market requirements (for casual workers, part-time workers).

Functions, tasks, composition structure and operation regulations of the National Salary Council are inadequate; The system of information and data for negotiation and agreement between the parties in the National Salary Council has not met the requirements; The process and authority to announce minimum salaries is complicated. Sanctioning of violations of the minimum salary is not strong enough.

Regulations on the construction of salary scales and payrolls are still rigid and inadequate (especially, regulations on the distance between adjacent salary grades at least 5%, the salary for jobs requiring trained workers) create must be at least 7% higher than the regional minimum salary ... has affected the structure of the salary scale, payroll of the enterprise).

For state-owned enterprises, the state regulates the salaries of managerial officials (ceiling level), which creates unreasonable salary relations in these enterprises.

Salary negotiation in enterprises is still ineffective, labor disputes and strikes are the most common causes of salaries.

Inspection, examination and supervision by management agencies are not regular or effective. Many businesses deliberately do not understand to force salaries, do not ensure full benefits for workers,...

The supporting role of the State to the enterprise in strengthening collective bargaining capacity on salaries, providing labor market information, helping businesses to improve the capacity of salary labor workers. The State has

not had much professional support, enhanced the ability to negotiate salary agreements, as well as formulated policies on employment and remuneration for enterprises;

The State has not fully assessed the impact of salary reform and policies related to enterprises and the labor market.

The cause of limitations

Vietnamese enterprises are mostly small and medium sized, low productivity, must implement low salary policy for a long period to attract investment as well as maintain and develop domestic enterprises.

The co-operation between regions, the slow reform of salary policies for the public sector has greatly affected the salary management in enterprises.

The work of propagandizing and popularizing the State's law on salaries has not been regular and timely.

Local state management apparatus is lacking in quantity and weak in specialized capacity (provincial and district levels).

The roles of Associations and Associations have not been fully utilized and promoted to the best of their ability.

In the enterprise, the awareness of the enterprise about salary policy as well as the implementation of the salary law is limited. The capacity of the contingent of labor and salary workers of most enterprises has not yet met the requirements. The grassroots trade union has not promoted its role, its capacity is still limited, dependent on the employer (for employment and salaries).

4.2. Recommendations to improve the state management of salaries in enterprises in Vietnam

4.2.1. Regarding the minimum salary

Continue to affirm the need for the state to maintain the minimum salary system as a tool to protect vulnerable workers, create a common safety net for salary workers in enterprises and regulate the labor market.

Periodically review and publish the minimum salary on the basis of the minimum living standard of the employee, in relation to the factors of the labor market and the ability of the economy. The zoning applies the minimum salary appropriate to the socio-economic development and labor market of each region. Set the hourly minimum salary, the roadmap to increase the minimum salary to gradually meet the living standards of workers (living salary).

Strengthening the organizational structure and composition of the National Salaries Council; Additional members are independent experts who have a deep understanding of salary labor.

Completing the process of announcing the minimum salary, spacing the time to adjust the minimum salary (about 2 year/time). Regulations on measures and sanctions are strong enough to ensure that enterprises implement the minimum salary.

4.2.2. Regarding salary scale, payroll

Continue to maintain the principle that enterprises build and decide on payrolls and salary scale that are appropriate for the business and public at the workplace. The State does not prescribe principles in the construction of salary scales and payrolls as currently (removing or reducing the minimum distance between salary grades, removing the minimum distance between jobs with hard labor conditions, toxic, extremely arduous, hazardous with equivalent work under normal conditions).

Research to assign 100% state-owned enterprises to build salary scales, payrolls and salaries for enterprise managers, ensuring a reasonable balance with the salaries of employees in each enterprise.

4.2.3. Regarding salary distribution

The State announces the minimum salary which is the lowest floor for negotiating salaries in enterprises. Enhancing the provision of labor market information, labor supply and demand, and employment information.

Request to develop and maintain a mechanism for dialogue, negotiation and agreement on salaries between enterprises and employees.

Clearly state the salary (salary) in the overall income received by the employee related to paid employment, to ensure contributions to social security (social insurance, health insurance, employment insurance, labor accident and occupational disease insurance, ...) of employees and employers.

For State-owned enterprises: (1) The State should grant autonomy to enterprises in determining salaries and bonuses for wholly state-owned enterprises and dominant State-owned enterprises; (2) Contracted salary costs; (3) Implement the principle of "who hires, appoints that person to evaluate the job and pay the salary", ...

4.2.4. Inspection, examination and supervision

The State needs to strengthen the inspection, examination and supervision of the distribution of salaries and incomes in enterprises. State inspection and examination activities need to be renovated in the direction of:

Having an annual inspection plan.

Grouping of enterprises for inspection: it is possible to group enterprises by the extent of occurrence of labor disputes or strikes; It is possible to group enterprises by the average salary, the lowest salary level of the enterprise, focus on inspecting and examining enterprises with lower salary policies than those with competitive salaries in the market. school, ...

Implement well the policy of inspectors by region, especially in regions where many businesses are located in the area. For regions with few businesses, it is possible to decentralize management to localities.

Establishing processes and mechanisms for self-inspection and supervision at enterprises. The state encourages self-examination by enterprises.

Supervise the implementation of the enterprise's commitment to corporate social responsibility in the salary policy to reward, honor, ... for the businesses that perform well.

Strengthen the inspection and examination in accordance with the law with the direction of inspection, examination is to do well the state management of salaries.

4.2.5. Developing training, consulting, and technical assistance on salary policy formulation in enterprises

The contents need focusing on include:

The State and MOLISA should have mechanisms to encourage the establishment of support centers, labor policy advice, human resource management, and salaries for businesses. Salary policy in enterprises is an important policy. However, in order to have a reasonable and scientific salary policy, enterprises need to have a comprehensive set of tools to perform such as: job analysis, labor norms, enterprise staff capacity framework, system. evaluate work performance, ... Therefore, it is necessary to have specialized staff in the field of human resource management of the Center to meet the needs of businesses.

MOLISA, Department of Labor - Salary Relations, Institute of Labor Science and Social Affairs, Ministry's Research Institutes should establish a team of experts specializing in training, consulting, supporting policy development. labor, salary policy of the business. Promptly support state management officials in salary of localities, as well as meet part of the demand for training, consulting, supporting, and transferring technology on salary policy in enterprises at present.

Regularly review and identify the needs of businesses, the difficulties and obstacles that businesses are facing, to have appropriate training and advice. There is a mechanism for information dissemination so that businesses can capture and know the registration channel and conduct training and counseling when necessary.

Develop a network of support, training, consulting to improve salary professional, improve collective bargaining capacity for businesses nationwide.

Encourage localities with the function of state management of salaries to enhance the training, consultancy and support functions of enterprises in improving the capacity of their employees' salaries and salaries.

Providing guidelines, instructions and support for the coordination and training links between the specialized training universities for human resource management, labor economics and enterprises. Encourage to strengthen this network, help improve the quality of training in schools, contribute to meet the needs of businesses.

The contents that need to be trained and advised should focus on: Skills of building salary scales and payrolls in enterprises; Guide methods of labor norms, support enterprises with labor norms; Capacity building framework; Establishing a system of performance evaluation and system administration; Advise, guide, support the arrangement method / production organization, workplace; Skills to develop pay plans, salary agreements, skills to build payroll rules; Implementation of labor policies at the workplace.

4.2.6. Improve collective bargaining capacity on salary

The State, organizations and enterprises should improve the capacity of collective bargaining for all parties in the labor relations of enterprises. In particular, focus on some basic solutions as follows:

Continue to stipulate the mechanism of collective bargaining and agreement on contents of labor relations. Encourage to improve the mechanism of salary agreement in enterprises through establishing a mechanism of dialogue, negotiation and agreement on salaries among entities in the labor relationship. Promote the formulation and implementation of substantive collective labor agreements.

Forming a mechanism for negotiating salaries at the enterprise level through collective bargaining in the direction of: specifying the collective bargaining mechanism, agreeing on labor relations, including the money issue. salaries between the two sides to sign enterprise-level collective labor agreements; Develop and maintain a mechanism for dialogue, negotiation and agreement on salaries between parties in labor relations.

Make publicly and transparently information directly related to the work, working conditions, salary, bonus ...

Facilitate and strengthen the capacity of the labor representative organization to take part in formulating labor-related policies in order to build a healthy and stable labor relationship within the enterprise. Focus on developing trade unions in all businesses. The State has a supportive solution to ensure unions relatively independent of employers.

V. CONCLUSION

The research results show that the state management of salary in enterprises in Vietnam has been renewed, perfected and achieved certain achievements. However, besides the achievements, the state management of salary in enterprises in Vietnam is still limited and inadequate, as the legal framework has many unreasonable points (regional minimum salary is not enough. life, the roadmap for change is not appropriate, the principles of salary scale construction are still rigid, unnecessary, ...); the implementation process and inspection are not really timely and effective; lack of the role, support and midwives of the State in strengthening the capacity of the labor and salary workers in the enterprise (when the capacity of this contingent in Vietnamese enterprises is weak), ... Therefore, it is necessary to renovate the state management of salaries in enterprises in Vietnam in order to create a favorable legal environment, business environment, and enhance the capacity of the parties to work towards the effective salary policy. As a result, it demonstrates the role of governance tools in the enterprise. Thereby, contributing to promoting progress and social justice in Vietnam.

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